

A Study on the Causes of Attrition in Call Center

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Introduction

A Call center is the place where telephone calls are either received or place in a very high volume. An inbound call center is a place where customer calls are handled by a customer service organization. Typically, a call center has a ability to handle a considerable volume of calls at the same time, aided by computer automation. An outbound call center is the one which you make calls. An example of this would be a telemarketing set-up where the agent make a large no. of calls to reach out to customer or a collection center.

Attrition of employees in the call center industry is mind boggling and it is creating havoc for the industry and especially for the HR Department. The attrition rate was not so high in any other new industry like telecom, retail stores, banking etc.

Working environment: It is the most important cause of attrition. Employees expect very professional approach and international working environment. They expect very friendly and learning environment. It is proved beyond doubt that Theory X will not work in the call center. It mean no bossism, rigid rules and strict / stick approach will not suit the call center. Employees look for freedom, good treatment from the superiors, good encouragement, friendly approach from one and all, good motivation and which is vary much as per the Theory Y of Douglas Mc Gregor.

Job Matters: NO doubt there jobs being lots of pressure and stress is high. The employees leave the job if there is too much pressure on performance or any work related pressures. It is quite common that employees are moved from one process to another. They take time to get adjusted with the new companies and few employees find it difficult to get adjusted and they have the job immediately. Monetary sets in very quickly and this is one of the main reasons for attrition. Youngsters look call center jobs as temporary and they quickly change the job once they get into their own field, under such circumstances, there are no solutions for retaining the employees.

Personal Reasons

There are many, but only few are visible, like

1. Getting married or falling in love or change in place
2. Health is another reason – employees do get affected with health problems like sleep disturbance, indigestion, headache, throat infection, allergic problems, etc.
3. Going for higher education like B.E, MCA, MBA and other GATE examinations or other examinations.

Background of the Study

Attrition rate is being considered as a serious problem in call center. Industry, especially call center is one the industry which have increased employment in India. Call center industry is the labour intensive industry. Employees are backbone of it, productivity, efficiency and advancement is all related to workforce to achieve these entire one should be committed to industry for the long-term. This in turn depends on the rate of attrition. Increased in attrition rate hampers industrial advancement, hence the causes of attrition rate in call center is shown for this study.

Statement of the Problem

The problem is “There is a dramatic increase in the level of attrition in Call Center industry”, the organisation is bearing a high cost is retention of employees studying the impact of various factors such as stress level, working hours, health factors and working condition which leads to high labour turnover.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the cause of increase in attrition in call center
- To know how to retain employees
- To study different methods which reduces attrition
- To know whether employees health get affected due to the night shift.

Review of Literature

Review literature survey revealed that very few studies were conducted in the field of attrition rate in Call Center. There was a very few secondary data was available on this topic. In Interaction in the HR Manager of various call center revealed that few studies have been conducted on this subject matter.

Analysis and Interpretation of the Study

1. Factors: Salary and Bonus

Rating	Highly dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Highly satisfied
No. of employees	3	26	25	13	3
Per cent	4	37	36	19	4

Analysis: The rating shows that 37% of respondents are dissatisfied, 36% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied and only 19% are satisfied with the salary and bonus.

Interpretation: The employees are not satisfied with the compensation packaged offered by the call center. There is a gap between what the employees expectations and what the industry offers.

2. Respect and Recognition from Management

Rating	Highly dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Highly satisfied
No. of employees	7	29	14	10	10
Per cent	10	42	20	14	14

Analysis: 42% is dissatisfied, 10% is highly dissatisfied, 20% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied 14% are satisfied, 14% are highly satisfied.

Interpretation: The majority of employees are not satisfied from getting respect and recognition from the management. The top management has to reward workers and make them know that they are important to the organisation. This gap has to be reduced by developing a better respect between management and employees.

3. Current work compared with previous work

Rating	Highly dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Satisfied	Highly satisfied
No. of employees	4	16	29	18	3
Per cent	6	23	41	26	4

Analysis: 41% are not neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 26% are satisfied, 4% are highly satisfied, 23% are dissatisfied and 6% are highly dissatisfied with present work compared to their previous work.

Interpretation: Majority of the employees do not find the difference with their previous working company and the present company. At the same time, few employees are satisfied and dissatisfied about their present job compared to the earlier job.

4. Training skills given

Rating	Yes	No
No. of employees	65	5
Per cent	93	7

Analysis: 93% of the respondents agrees that they have been given training for the required skills and few have disagreed that they have not been provided with required skills.

Interpretation: The call center industry has taken initiative in training their performed by training the required job skills, so that the employees perform better. It indicates that the organisation has been concentration on training and employees have been satisfactory about the4 given training.

5. Satisfaction with working hours

Rating	Yes	No
No. of employees	29	41
Per cent	41	59

Analysis: 59% have disagreed that they are satisfied with the working hours and 41% of respondent have agreed that they are satisfied with the working hours.

Interpretation: Majority of them are not satisfied with their working hours, employers perform to work in day shifts, although 41% have agreed that they are happy with the night shifts as many of them prefer to pursue their education in the day.

6. Job leads to increase in stress levels

Rating	Yes	No
No. of employees	50	20
Percent	71	29

Analysis: Majority of the respondents have agreed that the call center job leads to increase in stress level, 29 % of the respondents have disagreed in this.

Interpretation: Working in the night shifts and making calls which is a routing job does make the employees more stressful, this may lead them in quitting the job and switching over to day job.

Conclusion

To know the causes of attrition in call center is a major organizational tasks. The process often requires inputs from job holders, managers and training personnel and therefore needs to be carefully structured and directed. The analysis of result gathered is also an involved tasks and adds a good level of skill and understanding.

Causes of attrition in call center is the study conducted to determine the exact nature of the labour turnover problems. The causes of attrition in call center becomes the basis for recommendations about instruction and supporting organizational strategies and for enlisting support throughout the organization.

Recommendations

1. The organisation has to restructure the salary, so that the employees do not quite the job in search of another company.
2. The organisation has to ensure job security, by identifying the right employees, they can provide better incentives and salary for the permanent employees, and should assure them with pension relief after the retirement.
3. Regular training should be given to employees in various field and outbound activities should be organisaed by the team leader, so this motivates the employees to work for the organisation.
4. Various stress relieves exercises has be oranised so that the employees will not feel stressed to work in the night shifts, and also organisation has to pick there who are willing to work in the night shift only, this helps in reducing attrition.
5. The organisation has to have a policy, where it encourages its employees to pursue higher education which in turn helps the organisation in the long run, so the employees can have a growth in the same organisation and also they can improble their status in the organisation.

Bibiliography

1. Human Resource Management, Jan Beardwell, Lan Holden, TATA McGrow Hill
2. Managing Change, Peter F Drucker, TATA McGrow Hill
3. Human Resource Management, K. Ashwathappa, TATA McGrow Hill

Journals

1. Attrition Retention @ Call Center – Bina Rao, June 2nd 2004, Deccan Hearld
2. Managing Retention : IT & BPO firms take it to heart – 21st July 2004, Satya Prakash Singh, Times of India
3. Indian Call Center Industry Attrition Highest in Space – Economic Times

Websites

1. www.ovum.com/go/content/c%2c37283
2. www.expressitpeople.com
3. www.dell.com
4. www.mphasis.com
5. www.24/7customer.com